

Molybdenum oxide catalyst for wastewater treatment studied by faradaic efficiency

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ABSTRACT

The measurements of gas volumes evolved during electrochemical wastewater treatment provide the information on the process faradaic efficiency. This work demonstrates how it enables identification of the water oxidation pathway (2 or 4 electron) in flow electrolysis process through the application of the formulae suggested in the study. This way, the real wastewater oxidation strength, i.e. production of hydrogen peroxide can be determined based on calculations. These provide more accurate results than direct measurements of accumulated hydrogen peroxide concentration after the electrolysis process, as its instability may lead to its immediate decomposition and false results. As an example provided in the paper, the application of MoO₃ as a catalyst in the carbon composite electrode indicates almost no hydrogen peroxide detected after the process, whereas its oxidative properties owing to production of hydroxyl radicals demonstrate complete decomposition of wastewater analogue (methylene blue). The calculations point to high production of H₂O₂. Using pure carbon material without the catalyst in the same experiment, decomposition occurs at much lower rate. The possible mechanisms behind the processes are discussed. The approach presented in the work can aid to efficient development of catalysts towards two-electron water oxidation.

1. Introduction

Wastewater treatment plays inevitable role along with the depleting resources of salt-free water [1]. Recently, wastewater treatment technology via water electrolysis for a simultaneous production of valuable chemicals, such as hydrogen gas and hydrogen peroxide started to gain attention [2–5]. This allows for the enhancement of the whole process economy. At the same time hydrogen peroxide can be produced in a more affordable way compared to the current anthraquinone process [6]. Hydrogen finds its application as a fuel in fuel cells, while hydrogen peroxide is used in many applications such as bleaching or disinfection [7,8]. The disinfecting and oxidative properties of H₂O₂ may be used as produced, using wastewater as a feedstock, which seems to be the most efficient and economically justified [5,9,10].

While hydrogen can be produced in electrolysis process only during water reduction (on cathode), hydrogen peroxide can be obtained either as oxygen reduction reaction product (cathodic process) or as a result of water oxidation (anodic process) [11–13]. Electrode at which hydrogen peroxide is generally produced is selected based on the feed water properties and electrolyser projected application. Although higher

overall yields of H₂O₂ production as a result of oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) are noticed, the competitive water reduction to hydrogen is considerably smaller at the same time. This is important if the process is a part of an electrolyser for simultaneous hydrogen peroxide and hydrogen gas production [14,15]. On the other hand, if H₂O₂ is intended to be produced at positive electrode, then its production is competitive to the more facile oxygen evolution reaction resulting from four-electron process and two-electron process [16–19].

This is since two-electron oxidation is less preferred over the four-electron reaction as it takes place at higher equilibrium potential (1.76 V vs. 1.23 V vs. SHE at pH 0). Additionally, at these positive potentials the disproportionation reaction of decomposition of produced H₂O₂ (into O₂ and H₂O) can take place. This can effectively reduce the efficiency of the process, reaching some dynamic equilibrium between product formation and decomposition. It can be partially controlled using proper electrode materials, such as a suitable catalyst, which role is to control the rate of adsorption/desorption of reaction intermediates

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[20–26]. The current trend is based on searching for non-noble catalyst material instead of platinum group metals, which are scarce and expensive. One of the materials receiving attention in the field is molybdenum, which displays attractive and tuneable properties along with its high abundance in the Earth crust [27–29]. The combination of platinum group metal (PGM) and non-critical raw materials was also investigated in wastewater treatment field, which allowed for lower PGM loading [30–32], however, their complete removal is still challenging. Literature on the above-mentioned processes on their own is very rich, however, a process which combines the wastewater treatment with simultaneous production of valuable chemicals is more unique.

In the research on wastewater treatment, the quantity of produced hydrogen peroxide is often assessed via techniques such as titration with ceric sulfate, titration with potassium permanganate, UV–vis spectrophotometry with titanium oxysulfate, semi-quantitative peroxide test strips or rotating-ring disc electrode (RRDE) [33–37]. Unfortunately, all are destructive, therefore can only be used periodically during or after the electrolysis process by probe sampling. Moreover, the oxidation reaction mechanistic study can be done using Koutecky-Levich equation and rotating disc electrode (RDE). In case of RDE and RRDE, the average reaction electron transfer number and amount of H_2O_2 can be assessed only in special three-electrode setups. The quantification of gaseous products and determinations of their volumes (H_2 and O_2) is often carried out by water displacement method or direct gas analysis by mass spectrometry.

This paper presents a method which is using automated syringe pumps, as it is easier, more accurate, affordable and enables integration with additional equipment, e.g. additional gas analysis by mass spectrometry. Volume of gaseous product evolved at positive electrode and the charge passed enable Faradaic efficiency (FE) of oxidation to be determined using the Faraday's law. This allows for the calculation of ratio between two- and four-electron water oxidation pathways in flow electrolysis cell. This work contains FE calculations of gaseous product of oxidation to calculate the theoretical yield of hydrogen peroxide on carbon electrode. The calculated values are then compared to the experimental readings. Finally, the hypothesis is tested against an artificially added contaminant, methylene blue (MB), to track the oxidative properties of the electrolysis process [38]. The electrolysis is conducted using molybdenum particles at various oxidation state. The effect of oxidation state on the evolution of hydrogen, oxygen and hydrogen peroxide formation is additionally discussed. The aim of the paper is to demonstrate that the low yield of detectable H_2O_2 product is not equal to low disinfective properties of advanced oxidation process.

2. Experimental

Chemicals and materials. Chemicals were of >99 % purity and used as received. Molybdenum(VI) oxide, MoO_3 , was a starting material used to obtain MoO_2 and Mo in a reduction process in the high temperature furnace. The flow of hydrogen and argon mixture (1:9, v:v) was employed as a reducing agent. The whole process of reduction was performed according to the method described in the literature [39].

Electrochemical cell construction. The electrode was composed of a current collector made of stainless steel (316 L) and active material which was coated on the top. The electrode active material was made from a slurry of conductive ink containing MoO_3 , MoO_2 , or Mo particles which acted as electrochemical catalysts. The slurry was then applied with screen printing technique on the electrochemically etched stainless steel foil. The consistency of the paste was controlled using acetone. The final electrode was dried in an oven at 90 °C overnight.

Electrochemical setup. The electrochemical experiments were carried out using custom-made flow electrolyser system equipped with peristaltic pumps for electrolyte recirculation. The electrolyte (1 mol l^{-1} NaHCO_3 , pH = 8.13) was supplied to the electrolyser in a flow of 6 ml min^{-1} . Nafion 117 cation exchange membrane was used to separate anodic and cathodic chambers and to avoid electrolyte and gases

mixing. The correct flow distribution of electrolyte on electrode surface was provided by a porous glass disc. The working surface of the electrode exposed to the electrolyte was equal to 3.14 cm^2 . The systems were built in symmetric configurations, meaning that negative and positive electrodes were the same.

Analytical techniques. The concentration of the dye was measured operando using 625 nm diode and photodiode detector. The calibration and spectra were done with a UV–vis spectrometer (Metash) using pure electrolyte as a reference sample. Additional pressure transducers were used to control the pressure of the gases (anodic and cathodic) to be collected into syringe pumps using automated system with a micro-controller unit which were further recalculated into gas volumes.

3. Results and discussion

XRD spectra shown in Fig. 1 are obtained for pure molybdenum materials at different oxidation states. As it can be seen, all of them are of high crystallinity. Molybdenum(VI) oxide is characterized by numerous sharp reflections. Moreover, it matches well with the library data. No other forms of molybdenum were detected within this sample. The reduced form, MoO_2 shows smaller number of diffraction peaks, also well associated with the library data. Here, minor peaks from the intermediate form of molybdenum oxide (Mo_4O_{11}), and minor reflections of MoO_3 precursor are visible. In case of the entirely reduced material, Mo, four main diffraction peaks were detected. The smaller reflections between 25° – 30° 2 θ , were associated with the unconverted oxides (MoO_3 and MoO_2) as well as an intermediate (Mo_4O_{11}).

Another characterisation was conducted using Raman spectroscopy (Fig. S1). Clear peaks in MoO_3 identifying Mo – O bonds are observed at 800 and 1000 cm^{-1} . They have their secondary responses between 150 and 400 cm^{-1} . The appearance of these peaks in a molybdenum metal

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of molybdenum at different oxidation state: (A) MoO_3 , (B) MoO_2 , (C) Mo. Red colour indicates the library spectra (shown in the Figure).

(Fig. S1C) comes from the presence of small fraction of molybdenum oxides on the surface, not being fully reduced during reaction with hydrogen. This is consistent with XRD data, where negligible reflections from oxides were also detected. Additionally, as the spectra data were not smoothed, it is visible that the signal to noise ratio decreases with the degree of reduction, confirming the smaller contribution of given bonds.

Each electrolysis process using the molybdenum-containing carbon electrodes was carried out at 3 V for 25 min. This combination of voltage value and time duration was selected to account for ohmic and activation overpotentials in the system, and to ensure the production of gases will remain within the volumes of syringe pumps. These conditions enable production of quantifiable products: hydrogen, oxygen and hydrogen peroxide. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurement at 100 kHz indicates the cell ohmic resistance to be 30 Ohms for all samples. This corresponds to the voltage loss of more than 0.3 V when current reaches 10 mA (leaving the effective voltage to be around 2.7 V). Fig. 2 shows the total volumes of gases and hydrogen peroxide concentrations during the electrolysis.

The lowest volumes of gases evolved are detected using pure carbon ink as electrode materials. This can be due to low activity of the electrode towards gas evolution and high associated overpotentials. In case of molybdenum containing electrodes, a clear trend is observable. For H₂ evolution, its production decreases along with oxidation state of molybdenum. The situation is reversed for anodic gas evolution, where the highest production is observed when oxidation state of Mo increases. In other words, reduction is most effective on reduced electrode, whereas oxidation on oxidized electrode. This kind of behaviour can be explained as the electrolysis charge is consumed for reduction and oxidation of electrode material, instead of being used for water decomposition. Surprisingly, the amount of produced hydrogen peroxide does not follow any rule, although the positive potentials reached by all systems are within the stability limit of peroxide production (1.3 V) at the electrolyte pH (8.13). In fact, it is significantly higher in case of a pure carbon ink electrode, whereas in molybdenum containing electrode few times less.

According to numerous reports, metal oxides, including molybdenum oxide should facilitate two-electron water oxidation to H₂O₂. However, it might happen that the analysis of hydrogen peroxide product is not a sufficient indicator of reaction pathway. Hydrogen peroxide, although being produced in two-electron reaction, can be easily oxidized further to O₂ (in another two-electron reaction), giving only an impression of direct four-electron reaction, whereas it might be double two- electron reaction pathways.

It is possible to calculate the ratio between 2e⁻ and 4e⁻ water oxidation pathways to reveal the true production of hydrogen peroxide in real electrochemical flow cell. This is demonstrated here based on the analysis of faradaic efficiency towards oxygen production. This leads to an equation with a single unknown. Starting from the combination of

Faraday's law (Eq. (1)) and ideal gas law (Eq. (2)), one can derive the expression for volume of gas theoretically evolved in the process (Eq. (3)). Knowing the charge, Faraday's constant and theoretical number of moles of electrons, the volumes can be calculated. The calculation of gas volumes should always follow the assumption that it is the only product. In case of cathode, this number is 2, whereas in case of anode it is 4.

$$m = \frac{M \cdot q}{z \cdot F} \quad (1)$$

$$V = \frac{m \cdot 22.4}{M} \quad (2)$$

$$V_{\text{calculated}} = \frac{22.4 \cdot q}{z \cdot F} \quad (3)$$

The calculations of faradaic efficiencies are shown in Eqs. (4)–(6). The calculated values for hydrogen and oxygen production are visualised in Fig. 3.

$$FE(\text{H}_2) = \frac{V_{\text{H}_2(\text{measured})}}{V_{\text{H}_2(\text{calculated})}} \quad (4)$$

$$FE(\text{CO}_2, \text{O}_2) = \frac{V_{\text{CO}_2, \text{O}_2(\text{measured})}}{V_{\text{CO}_2, \text{O}_2(\text{calculated})}} \quad (5)$$

$$FE(\text{H}_2\text{O}_2) = \frac{H_2\text{O}_2(\text{measured})}{H_2\text{O}_2(\text{calculated})} \quad (6)$$

It might be noticed that the gases evolution efficiency is strongly dependent on the electrode materials. The highest efficiency of hydrogen evolution is ascribed to the most reduced electrode component (Mo), where it reaches 100 % and goes down with the increase of oxidation state. It follows also the potential of negative electrode. Anodic gas evolution faradaic efficiency, on the other hand, seems to exceed 100 % in case of two systems: carbon ink and carbon ink + MoO₃. Faradaic efficiency over 100 % should not normally occur. [40] The explanation is a false assumption of pure 4e⁻ reaction of water oxidation taking place. If a faradaic efficiency is at maximum 100 %, the calculated and measured amount of gas should be equal (Eq. (7) and Eq. (8)). Then, by combining it with Eq. (3), it will be possible to solve the equation for number of electrons (Eq. (9) and Eq. (10)). It will give the value of z between 2 and 4. Of course, if z = 2 then the reaction is purely 2e⁻ reaction, while z = 4 then the reaction is purely 4e⁻.

$$FE(\text{CO}_2, \text{O}_2) = 1 = \frac{V_{\text{CO}_2, \text{O}_2(\text{measured})}}{V_{\text{CO}_2, \text{O}_2(\text{calculated})}} \quad (7)$$

$$V_{\text{CO}_2, \text{O}_2(\text{measured})} = V_{\text{CO}_2, \text{O}_2(\text{calculated})} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2. Total volumes of gases and concentration of hydrogen peroxide during the electrolysis of NaHCO₃ solution at 3 V using carbon electrodes with different molybdenum additives. (A) hydrogen volume, (B) anodic gas volume, (C) hydrogen peroxide amount.

Fig. 3. Faradaic efficiencies of gases production during the electrolysis of NaHCO₃ solution at 3 V using different electrode materials indicated in the Fig. 2. (A) hydrogen evolution efficiency, (B) anodic gas evolution efficiency.

$$V_{CO_2, O_2(\text{measured})} = \frac{22.4 \cdot q}{z \cdot F} \quad (9)$$

$$z = \frac{22.4 \cdot q}{V_{CO_2, O_2(\text{measured})} \cdot F} \quad (10)$$

To be able to define the charge fraction, x , (percentage of charge, X) spent on specific reactions in the total electrode reaction, one should apply the relations in Eqs. (11) and (12).

$$z = 4x + 2(1 - x) \quad (11)$$

$$x = \frac{z - 2}{2} \quad (12)$$

The results indicate that the average electron transfer number in case of two systems: carbon ink and carbon ink + MoO₃ are 3.42 and 3.7, respectively. This stands for 71 % of charge spent on 4e⁻ reaction and 29 % of charge spent on 2e⁻ reaction for carbon ink and 85 % of charge spent on 4e⁻ reaction and 15 % of charge spent on 2e⁻ reaction for carbon ink + MoO₃. These percentage values and total charge values can be used to calculate the theoretical amounts of H₂O₂ produced, which are 30 and 78 mg l⁻¹, respectively. In case of carbon ink, the calculated and measured concentration is very close, however, for carbon ink + MoO₃ theoretical amount of H₂O₂ produced is much higher than practically measured. The hypothesis of this behaviour is that the charge is consumed in 2e⁻ reaction to produce H₂O₂ which is also decomposed in its oxidation reaction at the same time. It suggests that the adsorption of H₂O₂ intermediate is too strong and it becomes consumed at the same time as it is being produced. This is not the case for Mo and MoO₂, as the charge is consumed for production of highly reactive hydroxyl radical which immediately oxidizes Mo and MoO₂, diminishing the efficiency of anodic gases evolution.

Although the positive electrode potentials during the electrolysis are well within the region of peroxide formation, its concentration measured after the process is lower than expected. It is believed that the product is decomposed after being produced. The oxidative properties of electrolysis process are hereby verified using an organic compound as a wastewater analogue. For this purpose, it was decided to use methylene blue as it is possible to track its concentration via UV-vis measurement. Additionally, its UV-vis spectrum, in addition to its concentration, enables distinction between chromophore and benzene rings, thus informing about the degradation level of specific bonds in the molecule. It was added to the electrolyte at the concentration of 77 mg L⁻¹ MB + 1 mol L⁻¹ NaHCO₃, ensuring light blue colour. Its low initial concentration aims at mimicking the real conditions of the wastewater effluent from water remediation plant. Two limiting systems were selected to

demonstrate the oxidative strength of electrolysis process during advanced oxidation process. One (carbon ink), which produced measurable amounts of H₂O₂ and second (carbon ink + MoO₃), where no free hydrogen peroxide was detected. Table 1 provides the results of the electrolysis processes. Although the only difference with respect to the results in Fig. 2 is the presence of MB, the efficiency of electrolysis processes is considerably different.

The amounts of produced gases are different whether the electrolyte contains MB or not. In case of pure carbon ink system cathode, more negative potential limit led to higher production of hydrogen (1.17 ml vs. 0.85 ml). At the same time, more anodic gas was produced (0.74 ml vs. 0.53 ml), even though the anode potential was less positive. In total, higher gas evolution was noticed, at slightly lower charge passage. Higher faradaic efficiency towards anodic gas evolution and less positive potential value means less charge devoted to production of hydrogen peroxide. The amount of H₂O₂ was not measured as it is supposed to be transformed directly into hydroxyl radicals in advanced oxidation process of MB. Slightly different behaviour is ascribed to carbon ink + MoO₃ system. Similarly, depressed negative potential limit leads to higher production of hydrogen in the presence of MB than without (2.17 ml vs. 1.92 ml). However, the production of anodic gas is lower (1.07 ml vs. 1.28 ml). Lower efficiency towards anodic gas evolution, means higher production of hydrogen peroxide. In order to visualize and support the above considerations, Fig. 4 shows the dye degradation profile during the experiment which consists of four phases: flow off, electrolysis off; flow on, electrolysis off; flow on, electrolysis on; flow on, electrolysis off. First two minutes of no electrolyte flow and no electrolysis current indicate the concentration of the dye in static conditions, where it is confirmed that the concentration is stable. Then, the electrolyte recirculation is turned on, where progressive dye degradation is observed. Clearly, the decomposition is faster in case of carbon ink + MoO₃ system. The fact of decolourisation at no current conditions can be explained by the spontaneous catalytic effect, where MB undergoes oxidation and MoO₃ reduction. Then at time 0, the electrolysis starts and dye degradation is accelerated in case of both systems. However, again, the rate of degradation is higher for MoO₃ containing system. After the electrolysis is turned off, the degradation rates come back to their initial rates at no current conditions. In case of carbon ink + MoO₃ system deceleration of degradation is observed only due to the dye depletion and its lower availability in the electrolyte. To sum up, the electrolyte could be entirely decolourised using carbon ink + MoO₃ system, while pure carbon ink electrode only ca. one third of initial concentration. However, the downward trend of decolourisation in case of pure carbon ink electrode led to complete transparent solution after sufficient amount of time, here two days.

Table 1

Summary of the gases and hydrogen peroxide production, electrode potentials and associated charge in the electrolysis of NaHCO₃ solution with the presence of methylene blue for 25 min at 3 V.

Electrode	H ₂ (ml)	O ₂ (CO ₂) (ml)	Negative electrode potential (V vs. SHE)	Positive electrode potential (V vs. SHE)	MB degradation yield during the experiment (%)	Charge (C)
Carbon ink	1.17	0.74	-1.61	1.39	33 %	10.3
Carbon ink + MoO ₃	2.17	1.07	-1.6	1.40	100 %	17.0

Fig. 4. Concentration profile of MB in the electrolyte: (a) carbon ink electrodes, (b) carbon ink + MoO₃ electrodes. Electrolysis of NaHCO₃ solution at 3 V for 25 min.

The spontaneous decolourisation at electrolyte flow, but without current can be explained by an extremely efficient catalytic effect of MoO₃ where the MB dye undergoes chemical oxidation and electrode material reduction. The open circuit measurements in Fig. S2 show the behaviour of voltage and electrode potentials before and after turning on the electrolyte flow. It can be seen that the voltage drops immediately almost to 0 V in case of pure carbon ink electrodes. For carbon ink + MoO₃ system, initial drop only by 0.01 V is observed, after which a steady voltage decay is observed. The application of reference electrode in the measurement indicates that progressive discharge of positive

electrode (its reduction) is responsible for this behaviour. The spontaneous decolourisation and voltage drop suggest the ongoing Fenton like reaction, whereas its accelerated rate during electrolysis indicates the electro-Fenton like process. Often, the *in-situ* hydrogen peroxide generation is combined with a presence of Fe²⁺ ions in the solution to catalyse production of hydroxyl radicals in real electro-Fenton process. This was successfully achieved in [41] demonstrating decolourisation of MB, although it was done during cathodic production of H₂O₂. The electro-Fenton like reaction can also be stimulated using other multi-valent metal catalysts (such as molybdenum in this work). [42,43]. The

Fig. 5. UV-vis spectra of the electrolytes before and after the electrolysis process using two systems at 3 V during 25 min.

selection of metal for Fenton reaction and its targeted process (anodic or cathodic) will depend on the practical application.

Fig. 5 illustrates the initial UV–vis spectrum of the electrolyte containing methylene blue (blue curve), and spectra of the electrolyte after 25 min of electrolysis using two systems: carbon ink (light blue curve) and a mixture of carbon ink with molybdenum (VI) oxide (black curve). The absorption maxima which are characteristic for methylene blue are found at 246 nm, 290 nm and 664 nm. Three chromophores are responsible for the peaks: N, S substituted heterocyclic structure which is at 246 nm, benzene ring at 290 nm and dimethylamino group which occurs at the highest wavelength of 664 nm. [44] After completion of the electrolysis process, still the peaks are observed for carbon ink, whereas they vanished for the mixture of carbon ink and MoO₃. There are humps at lower wavelengths, which can be attributed to the residuals of benzene ring. This shows that the radicals formed with the presence of MoO₃ during the two-electron oxidation process decomposed the organic dye to a significantly higher degree.

4. Conclusions

The quantification of gaseous products amounts in water electrolysis enables the efficiency of electrolysis to be determined. An additional information of water oxidation pathway can be calculated on this basis following the approach presented in the paper. Although the concentration of hydrogen peroxide can be determined directly in the solution after the electrolysis process, its value is not always in agreement with the real amount produced. This is because H₂O₂ is an intermediate product which can undergo immediate decomposition in contact with organic impurity, especially in the presence of molybdenum ion catalyst. Its instability therefore leads to its difficult detection in these conditions. It is important conclusion in the research area where catalyst materials for two-electron water oxidation are sought. Here, it was demonstrated that molybdenum (VI) oxide is an interesting candidate for wastewater treatment, although traditional approach could exclude this material due to unsatisfactory results. According to the semi-quantitative measurements of hydrogen peroxide concentration, nanostructured carbon material exhibits higher tendency to 2e⁻ water oxidation comparing to molybdenum (VI) oxide. The measurement with a wastewater analogue, i.e. MB, which decomposition indirectly indicates H₂O₂ production, was tracked by UV–vis spectroscopy. It demonstrates that it is in agreement with calculations using faradaic efficiencies of 2 e⁻ and 4 e⁻ water oxidation reactions. Yet, equally important conclusion is that incompletely oxidised materials (Mo, MoO₂) are catalytically unfavourable for positive electrode material because they are rather being oxidised. Finally, the presented approach will contribute to actual effective wastewater treatment.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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